

HARNESSING BIOMIMETIC CATCH BONDS TO CREATE MECHANICALLY ROBUST NANOPARTICLE NETWORKS

Anna C. Balazs¹

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Pittsburgh
940 Benedum Hall, Pittsburgh, PA 15261 United States
Email: balazs@pitt.edu

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ABSTRACT

Using computer simulations, we investigate the mechanical properties of a network of polymer-grafted nanoparticles (PGNs) that are interlinked by labile “catch” bonds. In contrast to conventional “slip” bonds, the life time of catch bonds can potentially increase with the application of force (i.e., the rate of rupture can decrease). In effect, the bond becomes stronger under an applied force (if the strain rate is sufficiently high). Subjecting the PGN networks to a tensile deformation, we find that the networks encompassing catch bonds exhibit greater ductility and toughness than the networks interconnected by slip bonds. Moreover, when the applied tensile force is released, the catch bond networks exhibit lower hysteresis and faster relaxation of residual strain than the slip bond networks. The effects of the catch bonds on the mechanical behavior are attributed to transitions between two conformational states, which differ in their sensitivity to force. Overall, the results of these studies reveal that the catch bonds are useful for enhancing the ductility and toughness of the PGN networks; these improvements are due to catch bonds forestalling catastrophic failure of these materials under tensile deformation. The findings also highlight that the networks interconnected by catch bonds are resistant to fatigue as they withstand multiple cycles of deformation and thus, exhibit enhanced durability. These predictions provide valuable guidelines for fabricating a new class of mechanically robust nanocomposites through the incorporation of biomimetic catch bonds.

I. INTRODUCTION

The overarching question we aim to address is how to design functional polymeric materials that are simultaneously adaptive and mechanically robust. There is a tremendous need for functional materials that perform not only by responding to changes in the environment, but also by dynamically modifying their performance in response to these changes. Such materials would allow, for example, the creation of self-reinforcing, protective coatings or self-morphing airplane wings. To exhibit such adaptive behavior, the material must be both flexible and reconfigurable, which are properties typically associated with relatively weak structures. For use in various applications, however, the material must be highly durable. Thus, a critical challenge is designing materials that are simultaneously flexible, responsive and mechanically robust. We focus on polymeric materials because they are relatively mutable; our aim is to establish guidelines for also making them responsively tough and strong.

Biological systems have evolved to be highly responsive and adaptive; these characteristics are vital to survival. Hence, nature provides a host of design principles that could guide the creation of robust, adaptive materials that adjust their functionality in a relatively autonomous and self-sustaining manner. There are, however, two important stumbling blocks to “borrowing” from nature: isolating the optimal bio-inspired design concepts and establishing the most effective means of implementing these concepts within the framework of synthetic materials. Our goal is to use computational modeling to overcome these basic hurdles. Namely, computational models can pinpoint optimal regions in the design space that yield the desired performance, as well as produce totally new, expected behavior.

In recent studies, we are specifically focusing on bio-inspired mechano-responsive design elements.[1-14] In particular, we focus on the amazing properties enabled by catch bonds [3-14], which are “switched on” by mechanical deformation (as detailed further below). We concentrate on mechanical deformation as an environmental cue since this stimulus is not traditionally utilized as a route to controllably tailoring the properties of polymeric materials. Moreover, mechanical deformation has conventionally been considered detrimental to materials’ properties. Our goal is to establish how to harness applied forces to elicit a response that leads to significant improvement in the materials’ performance. To achieve this goal, we are developing foundational models to predict the performance of polymeric materials that encompass bio-inspired catch bonds.

Our preliminary studies indicate that catch bonds[14] hold the key to designing adaptive and robust polymeric materials. In particular, catch bonds bring unique features to the design space: they strengthen under an applied force.[3-13] In these studies, we specifically focus on cross-linked polymer-grafted nanoparticles (PGNs)[14-20] in order to tackle the daunting task of designing reconfigurable materials encompassing hard, immutable components. Inserted into networks of polymer-grafted nanoparticles, the catch bonds can yield composites that exhibit unprecedented resistance to deformation. If the nanoparticles are quantum dots, the catch bonds can be used to modulate the separation between the particles (as a function of force), and thus, controllably alter the optical signature of the robust system.

To date, there have been remarkably few attempts to harness these bio-inspired motifs in man-made materials.[21] Our findings can lay the groundwork for creating entirely new classes of strong, adaptive functional materials. Moreover, we will be disrupting accepted perspectives on the role of deformation; namely, we will provide guidelines for turning a potentially harmful stimulus into a vitally useful means of optimizing materials’ properties. Below, we detail the systems to be examined, discussing challenges that we must address in designing these new materials.

A. Designing Strong, Reconfigurable Nanocomposites: Introducing Catch Bonds

An important example of remarkable mechano-responsive bonds in biology is provided by “catch” bonds. Catch bonds play a vital role in stabilizing the rolling motion of leukocytes over the extracellular matrix in high shear flow. Catch bonds are unique because the bond life time increases with an applied force (i.e., the bond effectively becomes stronger under deformation).[3-13] Notably, there have been few attempts to introduce synthetic mimics of catch bonds into man-made materials, and thereby, create systems with remarkably adaptive behavior and tunable mechanical properties.

In these studies, we focus on cross-linked polymer-grafted nanoparticles (PGNs).[20] Here, the reactive groups on the ends of the grafted chains form bonds with neighboring chains, and thereby, interconnect the PGNs into an extensive material. We focus to PGN networks in order to address the intriguing challenge of designing reconfigurable materials that contain rigid solids, which contribute essential properties. Namely, the solid nanoparticles offer both valuable hardness and irreplaceable opto-electronic properties. The polymers, on the other hand, provide vital reconfigurability, i.e., the “strings” to manipulate the arrangement of the particles. PGN networks are a relatively new class of materials, and hence, there is a need for models that can predict how to optimize the performance of these novel composites.

To improve the overall strength and toughness of these mutable composites, we will incorporate “catch” bonds between the grafted polymer arms. A useful way to visualize the behavior of catch bonds is to recall the popular finger trap toy. You placed a finger in each end of the tube and pulled outwards; the harder you pulled, the more your fingers were bound by the tube and the more difficult it was to break free. On a molecular level, catch bonds operate in a manner analogous to this toy.

Put more concisely, the remarkable feature of a catch bond is that it becomes stronger when subjected to a tensile deformation. Normally, the life time of a bond decreases with an applied force,

as in the case of conventional “slip” bonds. For catch bonds, however, the life time of the bonds increases with an applied force. As noted above, catch bonds play a pivotal role in a number of biological processes,[3-13] but these distinctive bonding interactions have not been fully exploited in the design of synthetic materials. Thus, now is an opportune time to establish design rules for utilizing the properties of these interconnections, and thereby, paving the path for fruitful experimental studies. The introduction of biomimetic catch bonds could lead to dramatic improvements in the mechanical properties of materials under deformation. Integrated into flexible nanoparticle networks, these lightweight composites can exhibit unprecedented behavior. For example, these materials could yield: conformable coatings that become stronger as a result of an impact and, thereby, spontaneously form protective “armor”, self-morphing composites that adapt their structure to variations in local stresses, and materials that provide toughness “on demand”.

We have already begun to model these systems,[14] building on our newly developed models for PGN networks.[15-20] In our preliminary studies,[14] we modeled the effect of applying a tensile deformation to PGN networks encompassing catch bonds and found that these materials exhibit dramatically greater ductility and toughness than the networks interconnected by slip bonds. Moreover, when the applied tensile force is released, the catch bond networks exhibit significantly lower hysteresis and faster relaxation of residual strain than the slip bond networks. The effects of the catch bonds on the mechanical behavior are attributed to transitions between two conformational states, which differ in their sensitivity to force. These findings provide guidelines for creating nanocomposite networks that are highly resistant to mechanical deformation and show rapid strain recovery.

In future studies, we will vary the fraction of catch bonds, and thereby, fine tune the mechanical properties of the composite. Namely, by varying the relative ratio of the slip and catch bonds in the system, we can tailor the stress-strain curves of the material to exhibit a dramatically broad range of behavior. Hence, we can achieve the ultimate goal of designing materials to meet specified performance needs. We will also pinpoint parameters (including the strain rate) that minimize the hysteresis in the system. Hysteresis reflects the amount of energy lost, or dissipation, that occurs during the loading (application of force) and unloading (release of force) of the sample. The development of synthetic materials that exhibit very little hysteresis would be of significant importance to creating durable, energy efficient systems.

Through these studies, we are attempting to translate the powerful design concepts provided by biological catch bonds into synthetic polymeric materials. The findings can lead to significant changes with respect to utilizing mechanical deformation as a processing tool to improve materials' performance. Additionally, we are providing guidelines for “co-designing” the mechano-responsive elements and the applied force to produce unprecedented macroscopic behavior. Moreover, our results can provide fundamental insight into the relationships between microstructure of deformable materials, the internal structural changes that occur under external actions, and the resultant changes in properties. Through these studies, we are also attempting to make advances in computational methods, developing approaches that allow us to analyze and visualize changes across time and length scales. These findings can also facilitate progress in the rapidly growing area of bio-inspired materials.

Finally, we note that these studies can lead to the next generation of functional polymeric materials that not only adapt to mechanical cues in “programmable” ways, but also become stronger and tougher under deformation. Since we are focusing on a new class of materials, the studies can also reveal unexpected, emergent behavior.

II. INCORPORATING CATCH BONDS INTO PGN NETWORKS

In these studies, we consider networks formed from cross-linked polymer-grafted nanoparticles to achieve our goal of designing reconfigurable materials encompassing hard, immutable components. The combination of the grafted polymer “arms” (which provide the vital mutability), the catch bonds,

and the nanoparticles can lead to composites that are both reconfigurable and highly robust. Below, we describe the approach we use to model composite networks that encompass these unique bonding interactions[14] and then outline the new calculations we will perform in these studies.

A. Computational Model

The fundamental unit in our system consists of a spherical, rigid nanoparticle of radius r_0 that is decorated with end-grafted polymers, which form a corona around the particle.[15-20] The corona chains are in the semi-dilute regime and assumed to be in a good solvent; the thickness of the corona is given by $H = qr_0$. Below, all the length scales in the system are given with respect to the core radius r_0 , and hence, we consider a polymer-grafted nanoparticle (PGN) of core radius unity and a corona thickness q .

The ends of the corona chains encompass reactive groups and the reactive groups on the neighboring PGNs interact to form either a strong (“permanent”) or a labile bond. By means of these bonds, the PGNs are cross-linked into a swollen network. Both the permanent and labile bonds can rupture, but the only labile bonds can reform after they have ruptured.

In this coarse-grained approach, we model the interaction between two PGNs by a sum of interaction potentials: $U_{\text{int}} = U_{\text{rep}} + U_{\text{coh}} + U_{\text{link}}$. The term U_{rep} characterizes the repulsive interactions between the coated nanoparticles and is given by:[15]

$$\frac{U_{\text{rep}}(R)}{k_B T} = \frac{5}{18} f^{3/2} \times \begin{cases} -\ln(R/\sigma) + (1 + f^{1/2}/2)^{-1}, & R \leq \sigma \\ (1 + f^{1/2}/2)^{-1} (\sigma/R) \exp[-f^{1/2}(R - \sigma)/2\sigma], & R > \sigma \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here, f is the number of arms, R is the center-to-center inter-particle separation, and $\sigma = 2(1+q)(1+2f^{-1/2})^{-1}$ is the range of the potential.[15] The attractive cohesive interaction between the coated nanoparticles is described by a pseudopotential U_{coh} , which is constant for small values of R and balances the repulsion at the corona edges to allow for overlap between neighboring coronas. This potential is chosen to have the following form:[15]

$$U_{\text{coh}}(R) = -C \{1 + \exp[(R - A)/B]\}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where C is an energy scale, and A and B are length scales that determine the respective location and width of the attractive well in the potential.

The term U_{link} describes the attractive interaction between two particles linked by the bonded polymer arms. The attractive force acting between two bonded particles is given by:[15,20]

$$F_{\text{link}}(r) = N_b \kappa(r) r, \quad (3)$$

where N_b is the number of bonds formed between the given pair of particles, and $\kappa(r)$ is the spring stiffness, which increases progressively with the chain end-to-end distance $r = R - 2$. We use the following equation, obtained for a worm-like chain,[15] to calculate $\kappa(r)$:

$$\kappa(r) = k_B T R_0^{-2} \{1 + 2[1 - r^2 (2L)^{-2}]^{-2}\} \quad (4)$$

Here, $2L$ is the contour length of the chain formed by bonding two polymer arms of length L , $R_0^2 = 4l_p L$ is the mean-square end-to-end distance of the latter chain, and l_p is its persistence length.

The value of N_b in eq. (3) depends on the extent of overlap between the coronas of the nanoparticles and on the kinetics of bond formation and rupture.[15,20]

Beyond specifying whether the bonds are permanent or labile, we also identify the labile bonds as being either “slip” or “catch” bonds. The permanent bonds, on the other hand, are assumed to behave as slip bonds. The key difference between the slip and the catch bonds lies in their response to an applied tensile force, and in particular, to the force-dependent rate of bond rupture.[11-13] Namely, the application of force accelerates the rupturing of the slip bonds. For catch bonds, however, the rate of rupture can both increase and decrease, depending on the force exerted on the bond (see further below).

The effect of force on the rupture rate of the slip bonds can be described by the Bell model.[15] (In the ensuing discussion, the subscript P denotes a permanent bond and L indicates a labile bond.) According to the Bell model, the force exerted on the bond, F , acts to lower the energy barrier, $U_0^{(p,l)}$, separating the bound and free states, and leads to an exponential increase in the bond rupture rate, $k_r^{(p,l)} = k_{0r}^{(p,l)} \exp(\gamma_0 F)$, where $k_{0r}^{(p,l)} = \nu^{(p,l)} \exp(-U_0^{(p,l)} / k_B T)$ is the rupture rate in the absence of force.[15] (In the latter expression, $\nu^{(p,l)}$ is the characteristic molecular vibration frequency.[15]) The factor γ_0 in the expression for bond rupture rate is an adjustable parameter that characterizes the sensitivity of the slip bonds to the applied force. For slip bond formation in the limit of zero force, the ratio of the formation to rupture rate is given by $k_{0f}^{(l)} / k_{0r}^{(l)} = \exp(U_0^{(l)} / k_B T)$ [15] In general, the rate constant of bond formation decreases under an applied force.[15] For the sake of simplicity, however, we consider this rate constant to be a constant $k_f = k_{0f}^{(l)}$. [15-20]

The evolution equation for the number of slip bonds, N_b , can be written as:[15-20]

$$\frac{dN_b}{dt} = -k_r N_b + k_f P_c(R) [N_{max}(R) - N_b]^2, \quad (5)$$

where $N_{max}(R)$ is the maximum number of bonds that can be formed and $P_c(R)$ is the probability of contact of two chain ends on two neighboring PGNs that are separated by a center-to-center distance of R . [15-20] Note that $k_f = 0$ for the permanent bonds (they cannot reform after they are broken), so that only the first term on the right-hand side of eq. (5) is used for describing the evolution of the number of permanent bonds.

The notion of a catch bond was first introduced to explain the behavior of certain biological bonds that appeared to strengthen under an applied tensile force.[3] Atomic force microscopy and biomembrane force probe experiments demonstrated that such catch bonds ruptured predominantly at either low or high applied forces and rarely at intermediate levels of force.[4,6,12] A number of phenomenological models were developed to describe the rupture of specific biochemical catch bonds under an applied force. In these models, the catch bond behavior was explained through multiple rupture pathways within a single bound state or through transitions between multiple bound states.[6-13] Recently, it was observed that some relatively simple chemical bonds also exhibit behavior typical of the catch bonds.[14] The latter behavior was attributed to the dissimilar force sensitivity of the distinct conformational states of the bond.[14]

Notably, most models for catch bonds were formulated to describe the behavior of a specific biological system.[11] Our aim was to utilize a more broad-based approach, and hence, we

employed[14] a general two-state model[6,7] where the rupture behavior of a catch bond could be adjusted by varying a small set of model parameters. According to this model,[6,7] a catch bond has two conformational states, state 1 and state 2, which rupture with the force-dependent rates k_1 and k_2 , respectively. Transition rates between the states, k_{12} and k_{21} , also depend on the force F . The evolution equation for the number of bonds in each of the states, $N_b^{(1)}$ and $N_b^{(2)}$, is (cf. eq. (5)):

$$\frac{dN_b^{(1)}}{dt} = -(k_1 + k_{12})N_b^{(1)} + k_{21}N_b^{(2)} + k_f^{(1)}P_c(R)[N_{max}(R) - (N_b^{(1)} + N_b^{(2)})]^2 \quad (6a)$$

$$\frac{dN_b^{(2)}}{dt} = -(k_2 + k_{21})N_b^{(2)} + k_{12}N_b^{(1)} + k_f^{(2)}P_c(R)[N_{max}(R) - (N_b^{(1)} + N_b^{(2)})]^2 \quad (6b)$$

Equations (6a) and (6b) account for the evolution of the number of catch bonds in states 1 and 2 due to bond rupture, formation and transition between the states. The total number of catch bonds between two PGNs is given by the sum $N_b = N_b^{(1)} + N_b^{(2)}$.

The rupture rates in states 1 and 2 were modeled according to the Bell model as $k_1 = k_{0r}^{(1)} \exp(\gamma_1 F)$ and $k_2 = k_{0r}^{(2)} \exp(\gamma_2 F)$, respectively.[14] To reproduce rupture behavior characteristic of the catch bonds,[11,12] the force sensitivity parameters were assigned different values for the two states. In particular, $\gamma_1 = \gamma_0$ and $\gamma_2 = \gamma_0 / 3$. Hence, the rupture rate k_2 is less sensitive than k_1 to the applied force. For the sake of simplicity, both of the bound states were assumed to have the same zero force rupture rate, $k_{0r}^{(l)}$, which is equal to that of the slip bonds.

In describing the transitions between the two states, we assumed that at zero force, the transition rates are comparable to the rupture rates.[14] Further, we assumed that the transitions rates are biased such that 75% of the bonds are in the more force-sensitive state (state 1) at low forces, and that a rapid transition to the less force-sensitive state (state 2) occurs at finite forces. To achieve the latter behavior, the transition rates between the two states were chosen to be $k_{12} = k_{0r}^{(l)} \exp(\gamma_{12} F)$ and $k_{21} = 3k_{0r}^{(l)} \exp(\gamma_{21} F)$ at $\gamma_{12} > \gamma_{21}$. We chose these values of the rupture and transition rates to ensure that the two-state model captures the main features of the experimentally reported rupture behavior of the catch bonds.[11,12]

Finally, the rate of catch bond formation is partitioned between the two states according to the equilibrium partitions, $k_{21}(k_{12} + k_{21})^{-1}$ and $k_{12}(k_{12} + k_{21})^{-1}$, established due to the inter-state transitions at a given force. At the chosen values of the transition rates, the formation rate constants for states 1 and 2 at equilibrium separation, $r_{eq} = 1.2$, are given by $k_f^{(1)} = 0.46k_f$ and $k_f^{(2)} = 0.54k_f$, respectively, where k_f is the formation rate constant for the slip bonds in eq. (5).

The dynamics of the system is assumed to be in the overdamped regime, with the motion of each particle given by the equation $d\mathbf{x}/dt = \mu \mathbf{F}_{tot}$, where μ is the mobility and \mathbf{F}_{tot} is the total force on the polymer-grafted particle. The total force acting on a particle can be written as $\mathbf{F}_{tot} = -\partial U_{int} / \partial \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{F}_{ext}$, where \mathbf{F}_{ext} is the external force acting on the edge particles of the particle

array. This equation is solved numerically in two steps since the polymer spring force (within the expression for F_{tot}) in the dynamic equation depends on the number of bonds between particles, and consequently, on the evolution of the chemical kinetics given by eq. (5) or (6). In the first step, we determine the number of bonds at any given time, $N_b(t)$, by evolving numerically the unsteady-state kinetics, eq. (5) or (6), through an explicit Euler scheme with a time step of $10^{-2}T_0$, where T_0 is the unit of time in the simulation. Note that the numerical evolution of eqs. (5) and (6) yield real numbers, whereas the number of bonds $N_b(t)$ should take discrete integer values. To determine the integer value, we compare the fractional part of the numerical result, $\{N_b(t)\}$, with a random number ξ distributed uniformly between 0 and 1. If $\{N_b(t)\} < \xi$, then we truncate the result; otherwise, we increment the integer part of the result by 1. In the second step, we use this value for the number of bonds to calculate the spring force (see eq. (3)) in the dynamic equation and integrate numerically the resulting equation using a fourth-order Runge-Kutta algorithm with a time step of $10^{-2}T_0$. Finally, we related our simulation parameters to experimental values in refs. 14-20.

B. Preliminary Results

While all the governing equations in our model are for 3D systems (i.e., spherical particles with spherical coronas), the simulations described below were performed in 2D (representing a plane through the 3D sample). These preliminary results for PGN networks incorporating catch bonds[14] provide a strong indication of the potential of harnessing these interactions in synthetic materials. In particular, we calculated force (stress) versus strain curves from a loading and unloading simulation. Namely, the material is strained at a constant velocity—this is the loading process. (We note that the characteristics of the catch bonds become prominent at sufficiently high strain rates—e.g., on the order of 4 nm/sec in our system.) Then, the force is gradually decreased until it reaches zero—this is the unloading process. The difference between the loading and unloading behavior in a given curve is the hysteresis, which indicates the amount of energy dissipated in the system as the material is allowed to recover to the unstrained state. The exact procedure used to simulate the recovery process is detailed in refs. 14 and 19.

Here, $P_c=0$ refers to PGN networks that encompasses no catch bonds and are interconnected solely by labile slip bonds. On the other hand, $P_c=1$ represents networks where all the bonds interlinking the polymer-grafted nanoparticles are catch bonds. The bond energies for both systems are the same at zero strain, $U_0^{(l)} = 37k_B T$. We observe a dramatic difference in the hysteresis for these two systems. In particular, the system interconnected by catch bonds ($P_c=1$) shows significantly less hysteresis than the network connected by the slip bonds ($P_c=0$). Furthermore, the $P_c=1$ system shows essentially no residual strain (the value of ϵ when the force reaches zero at the unloading process). On the other hand, the $P_c=0$ system encompasses a considerable amount of residual strain after the unloading. We anticipate that by altering the strain rate in the loading cycle, we can reduce the degree of hysteresis in the $P_c=1$ system even further.

The distinctive behavior exhibited by the $P_c=1$ system indicates that these composites can be reconfigured without considerable loss in energy, i.e., the deformation of the system is relatively reversible. Notably, our preliminary results also show that this valuable attribute cannot be attained by simply increasing the bond energy. (For example, we set $U_0^{(l)} = 39.7$ for the $P_c=0$ system and the material still exhibited a residual strain of 0.15 after the unloading.) Hence, the catch bonds play a critical role in the low hysteretic behavior.

The behavior for the $P_c=1$ case resembles the performance of resilin, which is a protein found in many insects that enables them to pivot their wings with great efficiency (i.e., very little hysteresis).[21] The development of composites with such remarkable resilience could pave the way to fabricating hard, muscle-like actuators that would operate in a highly energy-efficient manner over multiple cycles. It is also worth noting that different biological muscles display different hysteretic behavior.[22] For instance, some muscles act as “shock absorbers”[22] and, thus, dissipate a significant amount of energy. By tuning the fraction of catch bonds in the material, we can begin to design composites that mimic the range of mechanical properties exhibited by biological muscles.

We observed another remarkable property of the catch-bond containing materials. Notably, we found a five-fold increase in the toughness of the material as the fraction of catch bonds in the system is increased. (The toughness is obtained from the area under the corresponding stress-strain curve.) The curve also indicates that the material’s toughness can be finely “tuned” by tailoring the relative fraction of catch bonds in the network. In effect, this attribute opens up the possibility of reverse engineering the materials to exhibit the desired properties. For example, given a specified toughness, we can determine the optimal combination of slip and catch bonds to yield the desired performance. By carrying out the specific studies described below, we can establish guidelines for fully exploiting the desirable feature of these materials.

III. CONCLUSIONS

Beyond the fundamental science that will be uncovered in the course of these studies, the proposed research will have a broad impact by guiding the development of entirely new classes of strong, adaptive functional polymers and composites. We note that developing these new reconfigurable materials could open new routes to low-temperature fabrication. For polymeric materials and composites, low-temperature formability promises lower energy consumption during manufacturing, reduced use of additives, faster production, and improved recyclability.[23,24] It is noteworthy that the field of “mechano-mutable” materials—materials that can be made to controllably change their shape and functionality with the application of force—is in its infancy and there is a tremendous need for predictions on how to utilize this mode of processing most effectively.

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